

EVALUATING SCHOOL CULTURE AS A BASIS FOR ENHANCING SCHOOL EFFECTIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

School culture plays a vital role in determining the success of students, teachers, and parents, as it shapes the institution's atmosphere, expectations, relationships, and overall climate. A positive school culture provides the essential foundation for student growth and achievement. It also supports teacher retention by promoting job satisfaction and professional development, while strengthening parental and community involvement, thereby extending the school's influence beyond the classroom. This study examined stakeholders' perceptions of school culture, focusing on the dimensions of unity of purpose, collaborative relationships, learning partnerships, and collaborative leadership. It assessed the views of employees, parents, and students regarding the school's effectiveness in terms of communication, instruction, and school atmosphere. Furthermore, the research explored the relationship between school culture and school effectiveness as perceived by employees. Findings revealed significant differences among employees, parents, and students in their assessments of communication and school atmosphere. However, no significant differences were found in their perceptions of instruction and overall school effectiveness. Statistical analysis indicated a positive relationship between the school's operational culture and its measurable effectiveness. Employees demonstrated strong commitment and upheld core values such as respect and teamwork, fostering unity among leaders, teachers, students, and parents. This shared culture contributed to effective school operations, quality instruction, and the holistic development of learners. Based on these findings, an enhancement program was proposed to further strengthen school operations and sustain a positive, collaborative culture.

KEYWORDS: School culture, school effectiveness

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a vital role in shaping individuals who can contribute meaningfully to society. Schools are expected to equip students with the necessary knowledge, skills, and values to meet both present and future demands. To fulfill this role effectively, schools must operate efficiently and align their practices with the principles of sustainable development. As emphasized by Abd Rabo and Hashaikeh (2020), schools are among the most significant

institutions established to promote learning and achieve educational goals. Thus, ensuring school effectiveness remains a central concern in the field of education.

A key element that influences school effectiveness is school culture. The fundamental personality of a school is formed through shared standards, attitudes, beliefs, and traditions among its members (Cooray, 2023). Each school possesses unique characteristics shaped by its goals and objectives, and this distinct culture gives meaning to its operations (Dimmock et al., 2021). Senol and Lesinger (2018) describe school culture as the collective expectations, principles, and customs that bind members together and create a supportive environment for teaching and learning. In fact, Duan et al. (2018) consider school culture as one of the essential requirements for a successful school.

School culture encompasses shared beliefs, assumptions, norms, and traditions that influence behavior and relationships within the institution (Gruenert, 2005; Karadag & Oztekin-Bayir, 2018). Although schools may share similar organizational structures, each develops its own symbols, customs, and practices that shape the attitudes and expectations of its members (Horton, 2018). Understanding this unique culture is essential for comprehending how an organization functions (Kalman & Balkar, 2018). Moreover, the attitudes and relationships among members significantly affect how culture influences thinking, behavior, and overall school performance (Widodo, 2019).

Research consistently highlights the connection between school culture and school effectiveness. Craig (2021) notes that when individuals are committed to shared missions, visions, and values, organizations perform at their best. Lezotte (1991) identified correlates of effective schools, including strong instructional leadership, high expectations, a safe environment, and active home-school relationships. Educational research further confirms that a positive school culture enhances teacher performance, student attitudes, and academic achievement (Leithwood & Sun, 2018; Jamaludin et al., 2019; Talebloo et al., 2018). Studies also reveal a positive relationship between school culture and school success (Duan et al., 2018).

In this context, the present study sought to examine the aspects of school culture and school effectiveness as manifested among employees, Grade 6 students, and parents of Doña Manuela Elementary School. The findings aim to provide a deeper understanding of how school culture influences effectiveness and to guide improvements in school operations. The study also ensures that all participants are provided with a safe and secure environment, strictly adhering to established safety and protection policies throughout the research process.

Statement of the Problem

The researcher sought to determine the aspects of school culture and school effectiveness as assessed by employees, Grade 6 students, and parents of Doña Manuela Elementary School. Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the assessment of employees on the aspects of the school's culture in terms of:
 - 1.1 unity of purpose;
 - 1.2 collaboration in relationships;
 - 1.3 learning partnerships; and
 - 1.4 collaborative leadership?
2. What is the assessment of employees, parents and students on the aspects of the school's effectiveness in terms of:

- 2.1 Communication;
 - 2.2 Instruction; and
 - 2.3 School atmosphere?
3. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of employees, parents and students on the aspects of the school's effectiveness?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the school's culture and the school's effectiveness as assessed by employees?
 5. What aspects of the school's culture are manifested by employees?
 6. What aspects of the school's effectiveness are manifested by employees?
 7. What aspects of the school's effectiveness are commonly manifested by parents and students?
 8. How can school culture relate to school effectiveness as observed by employees?
 9. Based on the findings, what are the proposed improvements for the school's operations?

Methodology

This study employed a convergent parallel mixed-method research design, where quantitative and qualitative data were collected simultaneously but analyzed separately to provide complementary insights (Damyanov, 2023; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). The quantitative aspect used surveys to assess the perceptions of employees, Grade 6 students, and parents on school culture and school effectiveness, while the qualitative aspect utilized focus group interviews to explore deeper experiences and perspectives. The integration of both methods enabled a comprehensive understanding of the problem, validated findings across datasets, and allowed triangulation of results to support conclusions.

For the quantitative study, the researcher used purposive sampling for employees (77 teachers and 6 non-teaching personnel) and random sampling for 156 parents and 156 Grade 6 students, determined using Slovin's formula at a 5% margin of error. Inclusion criteria required participants to have been with Doña Manuela Elementary School for at least two years, while newly hired employees and students/parents from other grade levels were excluded. A structured survey questionnaire adapted from Miller (2018) and Abd-Rabo & Hashaikeh (2020) was used to measure perceptions on school culture and effectiveness, employing a 4-point Likert scale. Reliability tests yielded Cronbach's alpha values of 0.826 for school culture and 0.893 for school effectiveness, indicating good internal consistency.

The data gathering procedure involved securing approval from the Division Superintendent and the school principal, followed by orientations for employees, students, and parents. Informed consent and assent were obtained prior to survey administration, which took approximately 30–45 minutes per participant. The researcher ensured the participants' privacy, safety, and voluntary participation, adhering to the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Collected data were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted using statistical tools including mean, independent samples t-test, and Pearson r correlation to determine assessments, differences, and relationships between school culture and effectiveness.

For the qualitative study, purposive sampling identified 30 participants—10 employees, 10 parents, and 10 students—all of whom had participated in the survey. Focus group interviews were conducted using open-ended guide questions to explore participants' perceptions in depth. Sessions were recorded, transcribed, and validated through member checking to ensure credibility, accuracy, and richness of the data (Delve, 2023). Ethical considerations were

strictly observed, including confidentiality, voluntary participation, and protection of students as a vulnerable population.

Data analysis for the qualitative component involved coding transcripts for recurring themes, identifying patterns, and refining main ideas to accurately represent participants' perspectives. Results from both the quantitative and qualitative phases were integrated to craft a comprehensive discussion, draw conclusions, and propose improvements for Doña Manuela Elementary School's operations. The entire research process, from topic generation to final submission, spanned approximately one and a half years.

Results and Discussion

This section presents of the data gathered from the survey questionnaire.

Assessment of Employees on the aspects of the school's culture

1.1 Unity of Purpose

This table presents the assessment of employees on the aspects of the school's culture in terms of unity of purpose.

Table 3. *Assessment of Employees on the Aspects of the School's Culture in terms of Unity of Purpose*

Description	Mean	Interpretation
1. Teachers, school administrators and non-teaching personnel support the mission of the school as mandated by the Department of Education.	3.86	Very much practiced
2. The school administrators ensure that the school provides a clear direction for all members of the school community.	3.78	Very much practiced
3. All members of the school community understand the mission of the school.	3.84	Very much practiced
4. The community's values and beliefs are reflected in the mission of the school.	3.87	Very much practiced
5. All the members of the school work towards the attainment of the school's mission.	3.84	Very much practiced
Grand Mean	3.84	Very much practiced

Legend: Very much practiced (3.26-4.00); Much practiced (2.51-3.25); Not much practiced (1.76-2.50); Not very much practiced (1.00-1.75)

Table 3 reveals that employees assessed the school's culture in terms of unity of purpose with a grand mean of 3.84, interpreted as Very Much Practiced. This indicates a strong alignment and commitment among teaching and non-teaching personnel toward the school's mission and vision as mandated by the Department of Education. The highest mean (3.87) was given to the statement that the community's values and beliefs are reflected in the school's mission, highlighting a shared sense of purpose and unity. Other indicators, such as supporting, understanding, and working toward the school's mission (3.86 and 3.84), further demonstrate collective dedication among employees.

The lowest mean (3.78), though still interpreted as Very Much Practiced, referred to administrators ensuring clear direction for all members of the school community. This suggests that while leadership is generally effective, there remains an opportunity to further strengthen clarity and communication of goals. As emphasized by Dogan (2017), effective school leadership plays a crucial role in guiding institutions toward success.

1.2 Collaboration in Relationships

This table presents the assessment of employees on the aspects of the school's culture in terms of collaboration in relationships.

Table 4. *Assessment of Employees on the Aspects of the School's Culture in terms of Collaboration in Relationships*

Description	Mean	Interpretation
6. All members of the school community assist one another in school activities.	3.86	Very much practiced
7. Teachers, administrators and non-teaching personnel are all willing to provide help or assistance when needed.	3.82	Very much practiced
8. Employees' ideas are valued and respected.	3.86	Very much practiced
9. All members of the school community can work in groups.	3.84	Very much practiced
10. All employees work together harmoniously.	3.87	Very much practiced
Grand Mean	3.85	Very much practiced

Legend: Very much practiced (3.26-4.00); Much practiced (2.51-3.25); Not much practiced (1.76-2.50); Not very much practiced (1.00-1.75)

Table 4 shows that employees assessed collaboration in relationships with a grand mean of 3.85, interpreted as Very Much Practiced. This indicates a strong culture of teamwork, cooperation, and mutual respect among teaching and non-teaching personnel. The highest mean (3.87) revealed that employees work together harmoniously, while other indicators (3.86 and 3.84) showed that members assist one another and value each other's ideas.

The lowest mean (3.82), though still Very Much Practiced, referred to employees' willingness to provide help when needed. This suggests that while collaboration is strong, structured support systems such as mentoring and peer coaching could further enhance relationships, consistent with Fullan and Quinn (2020) on the importance of collaborative staff in achieving school success.

1.3 Learning Partnerships

This table presents the assessment of employees on the aspects of the school's culture in terms of learning partnerships.

Table 5. *Assessment of Employees on the Aspects of the School's Culture in terms of Learning Partnerships*

Description	Mean	Interpretation
11. Parents and teachers have similar standards on how well the students should succeed.	3.52	Very much practiced
12. Parents have faith in the expert judgment of teachers.	3.70	Very much practiced
13. Parents and teachers discuss student achievement on a regular basis.	3.72	Very much practiced
14. In general, students take ownership of their education; for instance, they participate intellectually in class and finish their homework.	3.71	Very much practiced
15. Parents assist the teachers by teaching their children at home.	3.57	Very much practiced
Grand Mean	3.64	Very much practiced

Legend: Very much practiced (3.26-4.00); Much practiced (2.51-3.25); Not much practiced (1.76-2.50); Not very much practiced (1.00-1.75)

Table 5 indicates that employees rated learning partnerships with a grand mean of 3.64, interpreted as Very Much Practiced. This shows strong collaboration among teachers, parents, and students in supporting academic achievement both at school and at home. The highest mean (3.72) revealed that parents and teachers regularly discuss student progress, followed closely by students taking ownership of their learning (3.71) and parents' trust in teachers' professional judgment (3.70).

The lowest mean (3.52) referred to parents and teachers having similar standards for student success, suggesting slight differences in expectations. Parental involvement at home (3.57) also indicates an area for strengthening support, consistent with Kaplan and Owings (2013), who emphasized the importance of parental engagement in improving student outcomes.

1.4 Collaborative Leadership

This table presents the assessment of employees on the aspects of the school's culture in terms of collaborative leadership.

Table 6. *Assessment of Employees on the Aspects of the School's Culture in terms of Collaborative Leadership*

Description	Mean	Interpretation
16. School administrators such as the principal value the ideas of teachers and other personnel.	3.78	Very much practiced
17. School administrators such as the principal praise the good performance of teachers and other non-teaching personnel.	3.80	Very much practiced
18. School administrators make it easier for teachers and other non-teaching personnel to collaborate and work together.	3.70	Very much practiced
19. Teachers receive updates on school-related issues.	3.76	Very much

20. School administrators encourage all employees to share their ideas.	3.71	practiced Very much practiced
Grand Mean	3.75	Very much practiced

Legend: Very much practiced (3.26-4.00); Much practiced (2.51-3.25); Not much practiced (1.76-2.50); Not very much practiced (1.00-1.75)

Table 6 shows that employees rated collaborative leadership with a grand mean of 3.75, interpreted as Very Much Practiced. This indicates that school administrators promote participation, open communication, and shared decision-making among teachers and non-teaching personnel. The highest mean (3.80) revealed that administrators recognize and praise employees' good performance, which helps boost morale and foster a culture of excellence.

Other indicators, such as valuing employees' ideas (3.78), providing updates (3.76), and encouraging idea-sharing (3.71), further reflect transparency and inclusivity. The lowest mean (3.70), though still high, suggests room to strengthen structured opportunities for collaboration, consistent with Kruse (2021), who emphasized the importance of stakeholder cooperation in achieving positive student outcomes.

This table presents the summary of assessment of employees on the aspects of the school's culture.

Table 7. Summary of Assessment of Employees on the Aspects of the School's Culture

Description	Mean	Interpretation
Unity of Purpose	3.84	Very much practiced
Collaborative Relationships	3.85	Very much practiced
Learning Partnerships	3.64	Very much practiced
Collaborative Leadership	3.75	Very much practiced
Overall Mean	3.77	Very much practiced

Legend: Very much practiced (3.26-4.00); Much practiced (2.51-3.25); Not much practiced (1.76-2.50); Not very much practiced (1.00-1.75)

Table 7 shows that employees rated the overall school culture with a mean of 3.77, interpreted as Very Much Practiced, indicating a strong culture of unity, collaboration, and participative leadership. The highest mean (3.85) was in collaborative relationships, reflecting teamwork and mutual support within the school community.

Unity of purpose (3.84) and collaborative leadership (3.75) followed, showing employees' understanding of the school's mission and active participation encouraged by administrators. The lowest mean (3.64) was in learning partnerships, suggesting that student, teacher, and parent engagement could be further strengthened, consistent with Sangsurin et al. (2020), who emphasized that student achievement requires collaboration between home and school.

Assessment of Employees, Parents and Students on the Aspects of the School's Effectiveness

1.5 Communication

This table shows the assessment of employees, parents and students on the aspects of the school's effectiveness in terms of communication.

Table 8. *Assessment of Employees, Parents and Students on the Aspects of the School's Effectiveness in terms of Communication*

Description	Employees		Parents		Students	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. There is an open communication among members of the school community.	3.77	very much practiced	3.77	very much practiced	3.47	very much practiced
2. Parents are kept informed on the progress of their children in school.	3.81	very much practiced	3.88	very much practiced	3.82	very much practiced
3. Students and parents know and understand the expectations of teachers and school administrators to them.	3.63	very much practiced	3.72	very much practiced	3.63	very much practiced
4. The school administrators, teachers and other employees are open for dialogue to students and parents.	3.71	very much practiced	3.84	very much practiced	3.47	very much practiced
5. The school administrators, teachers and other employees are approachable and accommodating to the students and parents.	3.86	very much practiced	3.67	very much practiced	3.51	very much practiced
6. Parents are informed on the school activities involving students through different methods like text messages, letters, etc.	3.98	very much practiced	3.87	very much practiced	3.86	very much practiced
Grand Mean	3.79	very much practiced	3.79	very much practiced	3.63	very much practiced

Legend: Very much practiced (3.26-4.00); Much practiced (2.51-3.25); Not much practiced (1.76-2.50); Not very much practiced (1.00-1.75)

Table 8 shows that employees, parents, and students rated communication in the school as Very Much Practiced, with grand means of 3.79 for employees and parents, and 3.63 for students. This indicates that communication lines are generally open, and parents are satisfied with the information they receive. The slightly lower mean for students suggests that more efforts are needed to ensure they feel heard and well-informed on school matters requiring their attention.

For employees, the highest rating (3.98) was for keeping parents informed of school activities through various methods, highlighting an effective system for timely updates. The lowest rating (3.63) was for students and parents understanding the expectations of teachers and administrators, suggesting a need for clearer communication on roles and responsibilities.

Parents gave the highest mean (3.88) to being informed about their children’s progress, showing satisfaction with academic updates, while the lowest (3.67) was for the approachability of school personnel, indicating occasional limitations in interaction. Students rated the highest (3.86) for parents being informed of school activities, and the lowest (3.47) for open communication and administrator accessibility, suggesting a need to strengthen direct dialogue. Overall, the findings show that communication contributes to school effectiveness by creating a more cohesive and goal-oriented environment (Javornik & Mirazchyski, 2023).

1.6 Instruction

This table shows the assessment of employees, parents and students on the aspects of the school’s effectiveness in terms of instruction.

Table 9. *Assessment of Employees, Parents and Students on the Aspects of the School’s Effectiveness in terms of Instruction*

Description	Employees		Parents		Students	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
7. The school meets the learning needs of the students	3.69	Very much practiced	3.73	very much practiced	3.72	very much practiced
8. Parents support the activities given by the teachers to students.	3.73	Very much practiced	3.78	very much practiced	3.76	very much practiced
9. Teachers set high but achievable goals for students.	3.63	Very much practiced	3.52	very much practiced	3.72	very much practiced
10. Teachers evaluate student progress in several ways.	3.81	Very much practiced	3.72	very much practiced	3.81	very much practiced
11. Teachers encourage students to learn.	3.81	Very much practiced	3.95	very much practiced	3.86	very much practiced
12. Students are expected to achieve a high level of performance.	3.55	Very much practiced	3.92	very much practiced	3.73	very much practiced
13. Teachers use a variety of teaching techniques to maximize learning.	3.77	Very much practiced	3.73	very much practiced	3.89	very much practiced

14. The school supports learning by providing updated materials and equipment to students.	3.71	Very much practiced	3.67	very much practiced	3.81	very much practiced
Grand Mean	3.71	Very much practiced	3.75	very much practiced	3.79	very much practiced

Legend: Very much practiced (3.26-4.00); Much practiced (2.51-3.25); Not much practiced (1.76-2.50); Not very much practiced (1.00-1.75)

Table 9 shows that employees, parents, and students rated instruction as Very Much Practiced, with grand means of 3.71, 3.75, and 3.79, respectively. This indicates that all stakeholders perceive the school as effective in providing quality education and teaching strategies, with students showing slightly higher appreciation.

For employees, the highest ratings (3.81) were for evaluating student progress and encouraging learning, while the lowest (3.55) was for expecting high performance, suggesting room for innovation in teaching methods (Teig & Steinmann, 2023). Parents rated encouragement of students highest (3.95) and setting achievable goals lowest (3.52), indicating appreciation for motivation but a need for goal clarity.

Students gave the highest rating (3.89) to the use of varied teaching techniques and the lowest (3.72) to setting high but achievable goals. Overall, the findings show that instruction is effective, but continual adjustment of learning goals and teaching methods is needed to meet all students' needs.

1.7 School Atmosphere

This table shows the assessment of employees, parents and students on the aspects of the school's effectiveness in terms of school atmosphere.

Table 10. *Assessment of Employees, Parents and Students on the Aspects of the School's Effectiveness in terms of School Atmosphere*

Description	Employees		Parents		Students	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
15. Respect and trust dominate the school.	3.87	very much practiced	3.63	very much practiced	3.75	very much practiced
16. All members of the school community appreciate social and cultural differences at school.	3.94	very much practiced	3.61	very much practiced	3.86	very much practiced
17. The school recognizes student achievements.	3.88	very much practiced	3.89	very much practiced	3.78	very much practiced
18. Parents actively participate in school activities.	3.73	very much practiced	3.66	very much practiced	3.50	very much practiced
19. The school actively participates in different community activities.	3.76	very much practiced	3.85	very much practiced	3.71	very much practiced

20. The school surroundings are clean and well-maintained.	3.88	very much practiced	3.90	very much practiced	3.82	very much practiced
Grand Mean	3.84	very much practiced	3.76	very much practiced	3.74	very much practiced

Legend: Very much practiced (3.26-4.00); Much practiced (2.51-3.25); Not much practiced (1.76-2.50); Not very much practiced (1.00-1.75)

Table 10 shows that employees, parents, and students rated the school atmosphere as Very Much Practiced, with grand means of 3.84, 3.76, and 3.74, respectively. This indicates a positive, respectful, and conducive learning environment for all members of the school community.

For employees, the highest mean (3.94) was for appreciating social and cultural differences, while the lowest (3.73) was for parent participation, suggesting a need to further engage parents in school activities. Parents rated the school's clean and well-maintained surroundings highest (3.90) and appreciation of diversity lowest (3.61), indicating room to promote awareness of students' diverse backgrounds (Afemikhe et al., 2022).

Students gave the highest rating (3.86) to valuing diversity and the lowest (3.50) to parent participation, showing that while the school fosters respect and fairness, parental engagement in school events can be further strengthened.

This table shows the summary of the assessment of employees, parents and students on the aspects of the school's effectiveness.

Table 11. *Summary of the Assessment of Employees, Parents and Students on the Aspects of the School's Effectiveness*

Description	Employees		Parents		Students	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Communication	3.79	very much practiced	3.79	very much practiced	3.63	very much practiced
Instruction	3.71	Very much practiced	3.75	very much practiced	3.79	very much practiced
School Atmosphere	3.84	very much practiced	3.76	very much practiced	3.74	very much practiced
Overall Mean	3.78	very much practiced	3.77	very much practiced	3.72	very much practiced

Legend: Very much practiced (3.26-4.00); Much practiced (2.51-3.25); Not much practiced (1.76-2.50); Not very much practiced (1.00-1.75)

Table 11 shows that employees, parents, and students rated overall school effectiveness as Very Much Practiced, with means of 3.78, 3.77, and 3.72, respectively. This indicates general satisfaction with communication, instruction, and school atmosphere.

Employees rated school atmosphere highest (3.84), highlighting its role in achieving school objectives, while parents and students rated instruction highest (3.75 and 3.79), reflecting appreciation for quality teaching and varied strategies.

The lowest mean was for students' perception of communication (3.63), suggesting the need to improve feedback and information sharing, consistent with Demerath (2018) on the importance of communication in enhancing the learning environment.

Significant Difference in the Assessment of Employees, Parents and Students on the Aspects of the School's Effectiveness

This table shows the significant difference in the assessment of employees, parents and students on the aspects of the school's effectiveness.

Table 12. *Significant Difference in the Assessment of Employees, Parents and Students on the Aspects of School's Effectiveness*

	F	Sig.	Decision H0	Interpretation
Communication	19.273	0.000	reject H0	Significant
Instruction	2.067	0.128	accept H0	not significant
School Atmosphere	3.833	0.022	reject H0	Significant
School Effectiveness	2.639	0.073	accept H0	not significant

Table 12 shows significant differences in the assessment of communication ($F = 19.273$, $p = 0.000$) and school atmosphere ($F = 3.833$, $p = 0.022$) among employees, parents, and students, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that perceptions vary: students seek more ways to stay informed, employees value a respectful climate, and parents prioritize cleanliness and safety.

For instruction ($F = 2.067$, $p = 0.128$) and overall school effectiveness ($F = 2.639$, $p = 0.073$), no significant differences were found, so the null hypothesis is accepted. This shows that all groups share a common perception of instructional quality and the school's effectiveness in fulfilling its mission and achieving student outcomes, consistent with Eger and Prasilova (2020) on the importance of learning and instruction in school success.

Significant Relationship between the Aspects of the School's Culture and Aspects of the School's Effectiveness as Assessed by Employees

This table shows the significant relationship between the school's culture and the school's effectiveness as assessed by employees.

Table 13. *Significant Relationship between the School's Culture and the School's Effectiveness as Assessed by Employees*

		Decision H0	Interpretation
School Effectiveness & School Culture	Pearson r	0.763	
	Sig	0.000	reject H0
	N	83	significant

The Pearson r value of 0.763 (sig. at $0.000 < 0.05$) shows a significant relationship between school culture and school effectiveness as assessed by employees. The null hypothesis is rejected. The relationship is moderately high and in the positive direction. This means that as the school culture improves, the school's effectiveness also increases. School culture plays a significant role in increasing school effectiveness as seen in the work of Duan et al (2018). As employees see the school culture as characterized by trust, respect and open

communication, the more that they will be productive and motivated to achieve the school's goals.

Aspects of the School's Culture Manifested by Employees

Tables 14 presents the major themes and its sub-themes from the focus group discussion (FGD) made among 10 employees (7 teachers and 3 non-teaching personnel) on the aspects of school culture.

Table 14. *Table 14. Major Theme and Sub-themes on Employees' Manifested Aspects of School Culture*

Major Theme	Sub-Themes
Unity of Purpose	Cooperation and teamwork Respect and discipline Professionalism Communication and inclusiveness Religious and moral values Character formation Unity among stakeholders
Collaboration in Relationship	Works Collaboratively Respect the Authority and the elders Teamwork
Learning Partnership	Support programs and events Respect Religious and moral values Focus on academic and extra-curricular activities Work together
Collaborative Leadership	Traditions and Daily Routines Academic Excellence Cooperation and Shared Responsibilities

Employees described the school culture as grounded in unity, respect, cooperation, and shared responsibility. Under unity of purpose, Teacher 1 shared that the school “*promotes a culture of cooperation, respect, and continuous learning,*” while Teacher 2 emphasized “*discipline, punctuality, and professionalism.*” Respect is evident as students greet teachers properly and practice pagmamano, reflecting good values and moral formation.

Collaboration in relationships is shown through teamwork and shared tasks. A non-teaching staff stated, “*Teamwork and collaboration make the school effective,*” highlighting mutual support among staff and respect for leadership and authority.

Learning partnerships are manifested through support for academic and extracurricular programs. One staff member noted, “*The school has respectful students and kind teachers, and parents are cooperative,*” showing active involvement of stakeholders.

Collaborative leadership is reflected in shared responsibilities, school traditions, and commitment to excellence. Teachers highlighted regular assemblies, prayers, and values formation activities that strengthen discipline, unity, and student development. Overall, employees portray the school as having a strong, student-centered, and values-driven culture.

Aspects of the School’s Effectiveness Manifested by Employees

Table 15 presents the major theme and its sub-themes from the focus group discussion (FGD) made among 10 employees (7 teachers and 3 non-teaching personnel) on the aspects of school effectiveness.

Table 15. Major Theme and Sub-themes on Employees’ Manifested Aspects of School Effectiveness

Major Theme	Sub-Themes
Communication	Involvement of the Parents, Stakeholders and the community Strong Communication Understanding Leadership management
Instruction	Quality teaching and learning Student achievement Parental involvement Teamwork among staff Academic Performance
School Atmosphere	Safe Community Positive and safe school environment Active participation in programs

Employees identified communication, instruction, and school atmosphere as core aspects of school effectiveness. Under communication, Teacher 3 emphasized leadership authority, stating that the principal’s direction is followed by teachers, non-teaching staff, learners, and parents. Teacher 4 added that good communication positively affects learners’ performance, especially in activities like sports, while non-teaching staff shared, “*May mabuting pamumuno kapag nagtutulungan ang punong-guro at mga guro.*”

For instruction, Teacher 6 highlighted the quality of teaching, noting that teachers use different methods to ensure understanding. Teacher 7 echoed that effectiveness is seen in quality teaching and learning, good leadership, and a positive environment where everyone works together. Teacher 2 further emphasized learners’ achievements and active participation in academic and extracurricular programs, while Teacher 5 pointed out leadership and management, quality teaching, and a child-friendly environment as key to discipline and success.

Regarding school atmosphere, Non-Teaching Staff 1 described the school as “*positive, clean, and safe for students (ang paaralan ay may positibong kapaligiran, malinis at ligtas sa mga mag-aaral)*,” reflecting a secure and supportive environment that strengthens learning and partnership. Overall, employees view strong leadership, quality instruction, teamwork, and a safe environment as essential to school effectiveness.

Commonly Observed Aspects of School Effectiveness by Parents and Students

Table 16 presents the major theme and its sub-themes from the focus group discussion (FGD) made among 10 grade 6 parents on the aspects of school effectiveness.

Table 16. Major Themes and Sub-themes of School Effectiveness Commonly Manifested by Parents

Major Theme	Sub-Themes
Communication	Involvement of the Parents, Stakeholders and the community Strong Communication Understanding Strong and visionary leadership
Instruction	Quality teaching and diverse strategies Student achievement Parental involvement Teamwork among staff Academic Performance
School Atmosphere	Safe and child-friendly environment Parental involvement and communication Teacher dedication and student support Holistic development of learners

Parents manifested school effectiveness through active participation, open communication, and strong support for school programs. They value timely and clear updates about their child’s progress and trust the leadership of the school. Parent 4 shared, “*Sa nakikita ko effective ang isang school pag natututo ang bata at nag-iimprove talaga ang students, tapos ang teachers nagma-make ng effort para hindi boring ang klase,*” adding that constant communication with parents sustains school improvement. Parent 6 highlighted “*mahusay na pamamalakad at pamumuno ng principal*” and “*masisigasig na guro at de-kalidad na pagtuturo,*” with “*may suporta ng mga magulang*” strengthening programs. Parent 1 emphasized student safety, comfort, varied teaching strategies, and the principal’s strong leadership with clear vision. Parent 2 stressed quality teaching and fair judgment. Parent 3 pointed out strong leadership, high expectations, evidence-based strategies, differentiated instruction, and active engagement. Parent 5 noted teachers’ concern, good administration from past to present principals, and a child-friendly school prioritizing learners’ welfare.

Furthermore, parents described an effective school atmosphere as safe, orderly, respectful, and guided by consistent governance. Majority (Parents 1–7 and 10) emphasized safety, strong leadership, and caring teachers. Parent 7 stated, “*May maayos na pamamalakad, magagaling na teacher, maayos na kapaligiran, at magandang pakikipag-ugnayan sa mga magulang.*” Parent 10 concluded that competent and kind teachers and excellent leadership help students succeed academically and in extracurricular activities such as sports. Overall, communication, instruction, and school atmosphere are directly connected to school effectiveness, reinforcing both academic excellence and the holistic development of learners.

Table 17 presents the major theme and its sub-themes from the focus group discussion (FGD) made among 10 grade 6 students on the aspects of school effectiveness.

Table 17. Major Themes and Sub-themes of School Effectiveness Commonly Manifested by Students

Major Theme	Sub-Themes
Communication	Student discipline and good behavior Teacher dedication and kindness Clean and organized school environment Active participation in school activities Respectful relationships among teachers and learners Supportive and approachable principal

Students view school effectiveness through visible discipline, cleanliness, respect, leadership, and active participation. Student 1 shared, “*Ang mga bata ay may disiplina at sapat na binibigay na school supplies...*” (Students are disciplined and the school provides supplies for those who cannot afford them), highlighting inclusivity. Student 2 observed, “*Malinis tingnan at ang mga teachers ay hardworking...*” (The school is clean and teachers are hardworking), while Student 3 added, “*Masipag at magaling magturo*” (Teachers are diligent and good at teaching). Student 4 described the school as “*maganda at mababait ang mag-aaral*” (beautiful with kind students), and Student 5 said, “*Ang ating principal ay mabait at maganda*” (The principal is kind and nice).

Respect and positive relationships were consistently emphasized. Student 6 stated, “*Magalang at mababait ang mga mag-aaral*” (Students are respectful and kind), and Student 7 affirmed, “*Ang mga guro at mag-aaral ay magagalang at mababait*” (Teachers and students are respectful and kind). Student 8 noted, “*Nakikilahok sa mga aktibidad... palagi masaya ang mga guro at principal*” (The school participates in activities and teachers and the principal are always happy). Student 9 reiterated, “*Ang ating mga teacher ay mababait at magagalang magturo*” (Teachers are kind and excellent at teaching), while Student 10 concluded, “*Marami ang mga mag-aaral na mababait at magagalang*” (Many students are kind and respectful). Overall, students perceive an effective school as disciplined, clean, supportive, respectful, and nurturing.

Relationship Between School Culture and School Effectiveness as Observed by Employees

Table 18 presents the major theme and its sub-themes from the focus group discussion (FGD) made among employees on the relationship of school culture to school effectiveness.

Table 18. Major Themes and Sub-themes on the Relationship Between School Culture and School Effectiveness as Observed by Employees

Major Theme	Sub-Themes
Internal Commitment and Operational Practice	Commitment and continuous improvement Shared values and high expectations Recognition and motivation
Relational Culture and Supportive Environment	Collaboration and teamwork Respect and supportive relationships Stakeholder involvement

Employees linked school culture directly to school effectiveness through internal commitment and strong relationships. Teacher 2 stated that “*a culture of commitment and continuous improvement fosters teachers’ best practices as well as student engagement.*”

Teacher 7 added that a “*positive and respectful culture encourages cooperation, motivation, and commitment... which leads to better teaching, learning, and overall school performance with the help of the school head and the involvement of the parents.*” Teacher 4 emphasized shared values, noting that students show love for family and others and that “*teachers motivate them by giving rewards,*” making them “*more motivated to study hard.*”

Relational culture was also highlighted. Teacher 1 remarked that when teachers and learners share respect, teamwork, and commitment, it creates a productive environment. Teacher 2 stressed collaboration among school, stakeholders, and parents. Teacher 3 noted that teachers value students’ respect and discipline and mentioned Brigada Eskwela where stakeholders help the school. Teacher 5 stated that “*School culture is the foundation of school effectiveness,*” while Teacher 6 said, “*Kapag ang paaralan ay may kultura ng respeto at pakikipagtulungan, nagiging mas maganda ang performance ng mga guro at mag-aaral.*” Non-teaching staff affirmed, “*Nagkakaisa ang mga guro at mga magulang*” and “*Teamwork at collaboration kaya naging epektibo ang paaralan.*” Overall, employees consistently viewed teamwork, shared values, and supportive relationships as key drivers of improved performance and educational outcomes.

Proposed Improvements for the School’s Operations

Based on the findings, the following improvements are proposed for the school operations:

1. Unity of purpose
2. Collaboration in relationship
3. Learning partnerships
4. Collaborative leadership
5. Communication
6. Instruction
7. School atmosphere

The proposed improvement for the school’s operations is focused on strengthening a supportive environment where in everyone works together with the same purpose to build strong relationships and learning partnerships among the teachers, parents, learners and the stakeholder. The Collaborative leaderships should be encouraged all the members to have their voice in decision-making, while clear and open communication is also needed. Having clear instruction through effective teaching strategies will enhance student learning and the school atmosphere will help everyone feel valued and motivated.

Conclusion and Recommendations

1. The school demonstrates a strong and highly functioning culture in unity of purpose, collaboration in relationships, learning partnerships, and collaborative leadership; thus, these effective practices should be formally documented and institutionalized as the school’s official operating model.
2. Employees, parents, and students rate communication, instruction, and school atmosphere as very much practiced, indicating high effectiveness; therefore, these strengths should be sustained and showcased as models of excellence for other schools or departments.
3. Since stakeholders differ significantly in their assessments of communication and school atmosphere but not in instruction and overall effectiveness, the school should

conduct focused discussions with each group to improve alignment and address specific concerns.

4. The strong positive relationship between school culture and school effectiveness suggests the need to formalize and continuously monitor cultural indicators alongside effectiveness measures to support evidence-based decision-making.
5. The workforce's visible commitment to core values, courtesy, and cooperation fosters a positive environment; hence, a formal cultural mentorship program should be established to sustain and transmit these values to new employees.
6. As employees recognize teamwork, leadership, and a positive environment as drivers of success, the school should implement recognition and reward systems that reinforce these sustaining behaviors.
7. Parents and students perceive the school as a well-integrated, caring, and orderly community; thus, this positive public perception should be strengthened and utilized in community relations and engagement initiatives.
8. Employees view commitment, cooperation, and respect as essential to operational success and community involvement; therefore, dedicated time and resources should be allocated to activities that promote collaboration and partnership.
9. Given the school's strong culture and effectiveness, the proposed operational improvement program should be adopted and implemented to ensure continuous growth and sustainability.

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